

An Integrated MOOSE Workflow for Activation Modelling Using FISPACT-II and Cardinal

William Ellis^{1*}, Helen Brooks¹, Andrew Davis¹, Dave Foster¹

¹UK Atomic Energy Authority, Culham Campus, Oxfordshire OX14 3DB, UK

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803299

ABSTRACT

Activated materials are unavoidable in nuclear reactors. Neutrons resulting from nuclear reactions excite surrounding nuclides, which return to stable states via γ -ray emission. Accurate prediction of the resulting photon fields is essential for quantifying radiation hazards to maintenance personnel and equipment. Several methodologies exist for calculating dose rates from the resulting photon fields; however, assessing the broader impacts is a multi-physics problem. Phenomena such as photon heating require coupling with thermal analysis, while activation of fluids in the reactor environment needs to be modelled alongside computational fluid dynamics (CFD). This paper discusses the implementation of a FISPACT-II MOOSE application that enables the modelling of activated materials within an established multi-physics framework. We first test this application within a new implementation of the Rigorous Two Step (R2S) method for calculating shutdown dose rates (SDR), fully integrated within MOOSE. The approach couples FISPACT-II with Cardinal, which provides a MOOSE interface to OpenMC for particle transport. This integration enables automated SDR workflows, element-wise activation calculations, and parallel execution without manual data handling between codes.

We implement a distributed photon source sampling methodology, allowing processor-local sampling of decay photons. Benchmark comparisons demonstrate that the distributed sampling approach reproduces standard OpenMC results in the limit of large particle histories, verifying the method's correctness. This framework establishes the foundation for high-fidelity SDR simulations and future multi-physics analyses within the MOOSE environment.

Keywords: FISPACT-II, MOOSE, LIBRTI, Cardinal, Shutdown Dose Rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Material activation and the proceeding gamma emission are the primary contributor to shutdown radiation fields in nuclear reactors. Accurate modelling these fields is crucial in shielding design, maintenance planning, and multi-physics analyses involving thermal effects and fluid activation.

Several methodologies exist for calculating shutdown dose rates, one being the Rigorous Two Step (R2S) method. This method involves performing a neutron transport solve to calculate a spatially dependent neutron energy spectra, which is ingested by a nuclear activation code to calculate the resulting material activation and decay gamma energy spectra. The gamma energy spectra defines the source term for a photon transport solve, the results of which are used to calculate dose rate. Current R2S approaches rely on loosely integrated tools to perform these three steps (neutron transport, activation, and photon transport), increasing the chance of analyst error in routing data between different applications, and increasing the time cost of modelling. To address these limitations, we have developed a FISPACT-II MOOSE application, enabling high-fidelity modelling of activation, transmutation, and depletion within an established multiphysics framework, allowing for increased ease of communication with other applications. The first major use case in mind for this framework is estimating the shutdown dosage rates within the LIBRTI (The Lithium Breeding Tritium Innovation Programme) testing facility.

*william.ellis@ukaea.uk

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Overview and Design Goals

The goal of implementing FISPACT-II within MOOSE is to enable multi-physics modelling involving activation, transmutation, and depletion. Implementing FISPACT-II within a multi-physics framework allows coupling to other codes to model a wider range of phenomena, such as photon heating, activated fluids, and burn-up. As an initial demonstration, we embed the FISPACT-II MOOSE application within a fully MOOSE integrated implementation of the R2S method for shutdown dose rate analysis.

2.2. Dependencies

2.2.1. MOOSE

To meet these objectives, we opt to integrate FISPACT-II and our R2S implementation within MOOSE. MOOSE is a highly scalable, open-source finite element framework [1]. MOOSE is widely used on HPC hardware and scales well with increased computational resource, which will aid in performing high-fidelity solves. MOOSE provides mechanisms for wrapping external codes and controlling their execution within its environment. Through the `ExternalProblem` class, developers can control execution of external codes and manage data exchange between them and MOOSE. Crucially for our R2S implementation, this allows external codes - such as FISPACT-II - to be executed as part of a multi-app [2] [3]. The MOOSE multi-app system allows for a main application to instantiate sub-applications, each solving for specific physics. We run our R2S solve as a multi-app to organise the order in which applications execute, meaning the user only needs to run one initial program. MOOSE also offers a suite of existing validated physics modules that can be utilised in future work. For example, coupling the Heat Conduction module with our R2S implementation would allow for modelling of photon heating.

2.2.2. OpenMC & Cardinal

OpenMC [4] is an open-source, Monte Carlo particle-transport code. OpenMC is chosen primarily for its strong scalability with available compute resources, supporting shared-memory parallelism and distributed-memory parallelism, a mixture of both, and even execution on GPUs. OpenMC is also under active development with an increasingly broad feature set. Being open-source, it is easily extended to support specialised workflows. Furthermore, it is already wrapped within the MOOSE framework via Cardinal.

Cardinal is a MOOSE application wrapping the spectral element code NEKRS, and OpenMC [5]. Its verification suite provides confidence that the OpenMC coupling operates reliably within the MOOSE framework.

2.2.3. FISPACT-II

FISPACT-II[6] is a UKAEA-developed code capable of modelling activation, transmutation and depletion induced by neutron, proton, alpha, deuteron, or gamma particles [6]. Prior to this work, no MOOSE application wrapping FISPACT-II existed. We develop a FISPACT-II MOOSE app to enable its activation and inventory capabilities to be used within a multi-physics environment.

To utilise FISPACT-II's functionality within the MOOSE environment, we implement the methods provided by the FISPACT-II C++ API within MOOSE's `ExternalProblem` class, which defines execution and data transfer for external codes running within MOOSE.

Implementing FISPACT-II within MOOSE allows for the use of distributed-memory parallelism. MOOSE distributes ownership of mesh elements across processors, with elements allocated to a given processor referred to as "local". Each processor running the FISPACT-II MOOSE application solves only the

activation equations for its local elements.

2.3. The Rigorous Two Step Method

The rigorous two step (R2S) method for calculating SDR comprises three discrete stages. First, a neutron-transport solve must be executed to obtain the neutron flux energy spectra within different segments of the domain of interest. Second, neutron flux energy spectra are passed to a nuclear inventory code to model activation and transmutations occurring due to neutron irradiation. The inventory code calculates decay gamma energy spectra for each element in the domain. Finally, these decay gamma spectra are used to generate a source term for a second particle transport solve, which calculates the photon distribution in the domain due to the activated materials.

There are three primary aims of this R2S implementation. Firstly, it must enable the calculation of shutdown dose rates on high-fidelity models, providing a detailed understanding of localised dose rates. Secondly, the data transfer between stages of the R2S method must be automated, as must the instantiation of the individual applications. Thirdly, as we anticipate the need to couple the results with other physical models, it must be implemented within an environment that makes it easy to do so. This will enable the calculation of other physical phenomena such as photon heating or activated fluids within the same MOOSE framework. These capabilities move us towards using this methodology within a digital-twin environment.

Our method uses mesh tallies within the neutron transport step in order to obtain neutron energy spectra for each mesh element. The increased spatial resolution of per element activation calculations enables detailed analysis of localised irradiation intensities and nuclide inventories, compared to traditional cell-based, constructive solid geometry tallies.

2.4. Data Exchange Between Applications

Figure 1. Data flow between the MOOSE applications in R2S solve.

Transferring data between applications was the main challenge in developing our implementation of the R2S method. Neutron energy spectra calculated in Cardinal must be transferred to FISPACT-II for per-element activation calculations. The resulting decay photon spectra need to be passed back to OpenMC, and used to generate a photon source term. This section outlines the methods for transferring these data.

2.4.1. Neutron energy spectra transfer

To perform activation calculations, element-wise neutron energy spectra must be communicated from the Cardinal neutron-transport application to the FISPACT-II MOOSE application. The goal of performing high-fidelity solves forces us to consider the memory footprint of our chosen transfer method. Using the UKAEA-1102 group structure, each neutron energy spectrum will have 1102 bins. Assuming 8 byte doubles, each mesh element's neutron energy spectrum requires 8816 bytes of data. For a mesh of 100,000,000 elements, a number of elements reasonable for a high-fidelity solve [7], storing all spectra in memory would require approximately 0.86 TB. This excludes the amount of memory required for the transport and activation solves. Future HPC may alleviate such memory concerns, but currently a memory-efficient data-transfer method is essential to support high-fidelity activation workflows.

We transfer spectra via file-based I/O rather than in-memory variables. OpenMC automatically writes a 'statepoint' file after all particle histories are simulated, containing all the user requested tally data. Although file I/O incurs additional latency compared to reading from memory, this method significantly reduces memory usage during the solve. Figure 2 shows the main logic loop within the solve method of the FISPACT-II MOOSE application. By instantiating the neutron energy spectrum inside the loop, we ensure each processor holds only a single mesh element's spectrum in memory, minimising peak memory usage. Although file I/O adds overhead, its cost is negligible compared with transport and activation runtimes, making this approach a practical trade-off for memory scalability.

Figure 2. The main solve loop within the FISPACT-II MOOSE app, demonstrating the instantiation of neutron flux data inside the loop.

2.4.2. Decay photon energy spectra transfer

The FISPACT-II MOOSE application outputs element-wise decay photon energy spectra. These spectra can be used to initialise a source term for the Cardinal photon-transport solve. This requires transferring the spectra from the FISPACT-II MOOSE application to the Cardinal photon-transport application so they can be used to instantiate an OpenMC source term.

Standard OpenMC sampling requires serialising the photon spectra data across all running processors. This can incur additional memory utilisation. To avoid serialising the data, we introduce a methodology in which, during OpenMC runtime, each processor only samples particles within the mesh elements that were local to it in the FISPACT-II MOOSE application. This is implemented using OpenMC's CompiledSource functionality, which loads a shared library with defining custom particle sampling methods.

2.5. Compiled Source Implementation

OpenMC's `OpenMC::CompiledSource` interface allows for the use of a simulation source defined by methods in a compiled shared library. We implement a custom source library that samples decay photons from the spectra generated by FISPACT-II. To communicate the photon spectra calculated

to the `CompiledSource`, we utilise interprocess memory communication (IPC) to share data between the FISPACT-II and OpenMC processes. Specifically, we employ `Boost::Interprocess` [8] to create shared-memory segments accessible across processes. During runtime of the FISPACT-II MOOSE app, each processor writes the photon spectra for its local elements into its own shared-memory segment. This memory segment is persistent even after the process that generated it finishes. Therefore, after the FISPACT-II MOOSE application exits, methods defined in the `CompiledSource` can still access the photon spectra data. Each processor running OpenMC reads only from its corresponding interprocess segment, and samples photons within the same mesh elements it owned during the FISPACT-II solve. Hence, only the local photon energy spectra are required.

Each processor samples an approximately equal number of particles, but the strength of their local source terms may differ. Therefore, each sampled particle is weighted according to the relative contribution of its processors' local source strength to the domain-wide source strength. Equation 1 details how the weighting of each sampled particle is calculated.

$$\text{Particle Weight} = \frac{\text{Local Source Intensity}}{\text{Total Source Intensity}} * \text{num_sources} \quad (1)$$

2.6. Testing Methodology

To verify the implementation of the distributed sampling method, we use a simple cubic test geometry. We compare the results of the distributed sampling method (using the `CompiledSource`) with those obtained using an `OpenMC::MeshSource`, which serves as a reference method. An `OpenMC::MeshSource` is an OpenMC source object in which the source term is defined using an unstructured mesh, with each element having its own independent source term. In this methodology, each processor samples over the entire domain, requiring the photon energy spectra for each element to be serialised across all processors, thus increasing memory usage.

To isolate and test the distributed sampling method, we do not perform the neutron-transport or the activation solve. Instead, both methods use synthetic "decay photon" spectra for each element, with linearly increasing intensity along the X axis. This isolates the behaviour of the interprocess data transfer and the sampling methodology.

We use three test cases to compare the `MeshSource` and distributed sampling methods. First, the initial sampled coordinates of the particles within the simulations will be compared. This assesses whether distributed sampling correctly restricts each processor to its local mesh region. Both simulations use 8 processors.

Second we compare the results using only 1 processor. Using distributed sampling with a single processor should yield identical results to the `MeshSource`, since the rank owns the full mesh and all spectra; this provides a baseline correctness check.

Third, both sampling methods are compared using an increasing number of particle histories. Both tests are run using 8 processors. Given the implicit differences in the sampled particle locations in both methodologies, we expect to see convergence within limit of large particle histories.

3. DISTRIBUTED SAMPLING RESULTS

Figure 3 compares the initial positions of sampled particles using both the `MeshSource` and the distributed sampling. Each marker indicates a particle, and all the particles are colour-coded according to the processor that sampled them. Figure 3a shows clearly separated colour regions, demonstrating that each processor samples only within its assigned mesh partition, as intended. In contrast, Figure 3b shows no processor specific clustering, confirming that each processor samples across the full domain when spectra are serialised globally.

Figure 3. Sampled particle initial coordinates for both the (a) *MeshSource* sampling and (b) distributed sampling, coloured by processor ID.

Figure 4. The average percentage difference in element fluxes between the *MeshSource* and distributed sampling methods as more particle histories are simulated.

Figure 4 demonstrates convergence between the two methods as particle histories increase, indicating statistical equivalence in the limit of large numbers. As more particle histories are simulated, the two methods converge on a similar flux distribution.

Figure 5 compares the particle flux results achieved using both methodologies, when running on a single processor. The flux tallies match element by element to within double-precision rounding error. This is expected, as when running on a single processor, the distributed sampling method is sampling over the entire domain and all spectra reside on one processor, mimicking the behaviour of the *MeshSource*. This result further verifies the implementation of the distributed sampling method, as when initialised with the same random seed and given identical sampling conditions, it reproduces *MeshSource* results exactly. These results verify that distributed sampling reproduces *MeshSource* behaviour without re-

Figure 5. Photon flux distributions for both the (a) MeshSource sampling and (b) the distributed sampling with 1 MPI rank.

quiring global serialisation of photon spectra, enabling scalable SDR calculations on large meshes

4. OUTLOOK

Future work will validate this implementation of the R2S method using benchmarks from the SINBAD database, specifically data from the Frascati Neutron Generator (FNG) [9]. Experimental results from the FNG have been used extensively to validate shutdown dose rate calculations. Unfortunately, the source term and geometry provided in the SINBAD benchmark case are only provided in a suitable format for use in MCNP. To perform our own validation requires a significant effort to translate these inputs into a format suitable for OpenMC. So far the geometry and neutron source term have been translated, and are currently undergoing their own validation before they are used to perform any shutdown dosage rate calculations. Figure 6 shows preliminary results for neutron flux distribution using the OpenMC implemented neutron source.

Figure 6. Preliminary OpenMC results of the neutron flux distribution across the Frascati Neutron Generator.

Once validated, we intend to use this methodology to run SDR calculations on high fidelity models, including tokamak scale models [7], to help compare memory utilisation between standard methods and the distributed methods. Although the test cases presented here are too small to expose substantial memory savings, we expect the benefits of distributed sampling to become significant on large-scale meshes. Furthermore, we will look at coupling this approach within broader multi-physics simulations to model phenomena such as photon heating, and activated fluids.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The early results shown demonstrate the validity of this approach to the R2S method. The distributed sampling methodology is successfully validated against the standard MeshSource approach and provides a scalable sampling solution that avoids serialisation. This approach enables shutdown dose-rate calculations on high fidelity meshes. By implementing FISPACT-II within the MOOSE environment, we have enabled fully coupled multi-physics simulations incorporating activation, transmutation, and depletion, that can be combined with thermal, fluid, and structural modules in the same framework. We look to utilise this capability in more complex multi-physics modelling scenarios moving forward.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Harbour, G. Giudicelli, A. D. Lindsay, P. German, et al. "4.0 MOOSE: Enabling massively parallel Multiphysics simulation." *SoftwareX*, **volume 31**, p. 102264 (2025). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352711025002316>.
- [2] G. L. Giudicelli, F. Kong, R. Stogner, L. Harbour, D. Gaston, A. Lindsay, Z. Prince, L. Charlot, S. Terlizzi, M. Eltawila, and A. Novak. "Data transfers for nuclear reactor multiphysics studies using the MOOSE framework." *Frontiers in Nuclear Engineering*, **volume Volume 4 - 2025** (2025). URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/nuclear-engineering/articles/10.3389/fnuen.2025.1611173>.
- [3] D. R. Gaston, C. J. Permann, J. W. Peterson, A. E. Slaughter, D. Andrš, Y. Wang, et al. "Physics-based multiscale coupling for full core nuclear reactor simulation." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 84**, pp. 45–54 (2015).
- [4] P. Romano, N. Horelik, B. Herman, A. Nelson, B. Forget, and K. Smith. "OpenMC: A State-of-the-Art Monte Carlo Code for Research and Development." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 90–97 (2015). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030645491400379X>.
- [5] A. Novak, D. Andrs, P. Shriwise, J. Fang, H. Yuan, D. Shaver, E. Merzari, P. Romano, and R. Martineau. "Coupled Monte Carlo and Thermal-Fluid Modeling of High Temperature Gas Reactors Using Cardinal." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 177**, p. 109310 (2022). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454922003450>.
- [6] J.-C. Sublet, J. Eastwood, J. Morgan, M. Gilbert, M. Fleming, and W. Arter. "FISPACT-II: An Advanced Simulation System for Activation, Transmutation and Material Modelling." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 139**, pp. 77–137 (2017). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0090375217300029>. Special Issue on Nuclear Reaction Data.
- [7] W. Ellis, L. Reali, A. Davis, H. Brooks, I. Katramados, A. Thornton, R. Akers, and S. Dudarev. "Mechanical model for a full fusion tokamak enabled by supercomputing." *Nuclear Fusion*, **volume 65**(3), p. 036033 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-4326/adb443>.
- [8] Boost. "Boost C++ Libraries." <http://www.boost.org/> (2015). Last accessed 2015-06-30.
- [9] I. A. Kodeli and E. Sartori. "SINBAD – Radiation shielding benchmark experiments." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 159**, p. 108254 (2021). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454921001304>.